

UZAY EKONOMİSİNDE KÜRESEL ASİMETRİ VE DIŞSALLIKLAR: DİJİTAL KOLONYALİZM VE YENİ BAĞIMLILIK DÖNGÜSÜ

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18099489

Makale Türü: Araştırma

Geliş Tarihi: 05.10.2025

Kabul Tarihi: 16.12.2025

Bu makaleye atıfta bulunmak için:
Südüpak, Ö. B. (2025). Uzay ekonomisinde küresel asimetri ve dışsallıklar: Dijital kolonyalizm ve yeni bağımlılık döngüsü. *ETÜ Sentez İktisadi ve İdari Bilimler Dergisi*. 16, 153-168.

Öz: Bu çalışma, uzay ekonomisinin yalnızca teknolojik bir alan değil; aynı zamanda küresel adalet, veri egemenliği ve kamusal fayda çerçevesinde değerlendirilmesi gereken çok boyutlu bir yapı sunduğunu ortaya koymaktadır. Uydu teknolojileri, konumlandırma sistemleri ve gözlem verileri aracılığıyla ekonomik büyümenin yanı sıra afet yönetimi, tarım ve çevresel sürdürülebilirlik gibi alanlarda pozitif dışsallıklar üretmektedir. Ancak, bu altyapılar üzerindeki mülkiyetin ve veri kontrolünün az sayıda aktörde yoğunlaşması, dijital kolonyalizm kavramını güncel uzay politikalarının merkezine taşımaktadır. Çalışma, Andre Gunder Frank'ın Bağımlılık Teorisi üzerinden, çevre ülkelerin yalnızca veri tüketicisi konumunda kaldığını; üretim, fırlatma ve spektrum yönetimi gibi stratejik segmentlerde merkez ülkelere bağımlı olduğunu savunmaktadır. Sonuç bölümünde, uzay altyapılarının demokratikleşmesi için veri erişiminin kamusallaştırılması, bağımsız fırlatma kabiliyetlerinin geliştirilmesi ve uluslararası yönetim ilkelerinin güçlendirilmesi gerektiği vurgulanmaktadır. Böylelikle uzay ekonomisinin sadece teknolojik değil, aynı zamanda sosyal eşitliği gözetilen bir alan hâline gelmesi amaçlanmaktadır.

Anahtar Kelimeler : Kolonyalizm, Dışsallıklar, Uzay Ekonomisi

Jel Kodları : F54, D62, L96

GLOBAL ASYMMETRY AND EXTERNALITIES IN THE SPACE ECONOMY: DIGITAL COLONIALISM AND THE NEW CYCLE OF DEPENDENCE

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18099489

Article Type: Research

Received Date: 05.10.2025

Accepted Date: 16.12.2025

To cite this article:

Südüpak, Ö. B. (2025). Global asymmetry and externalities in the space economy: Digital colonialism and the new cycle of dependence. *ETU Synthesis Journal of Economics and Administrative Sciences*. 16, 153-168.

Abstract: This article argues that the space economy is not just a technological frontier, but a multidimensional realm that encompasses global justice, data sovereignty, and the provision of public goods. Satellite-based systems, positioning systems, and earth observation data produce significant positive externalities in various areas, including disaster prevention, agriculture, and environmental protection. However, the consolidation of ownership and control over these infrastructures in the hands of just a few major entities is also making these forms of digital colonialism more menacing. Based on Andre Gunder Frank's Dependency Theory, the study argues that peripheral countries are mere consumers of space-based information, deprived of independence in high-value sectors such as satellite manufacturing, launching systems, and spectrum allocation. The analysis highlights that, despite tangible advances in satellite ownership, profound structural imbalances persist. In short, democratizing the space economy entails making information public, fostering competition among launchers, and enhancing international governance. These are necessary measures to ensure that space infrastructures grow, not just as technologies, but as engines of social justice and equitable global development.

Keywords : Colonialism, Externalities, Space Economy

Jel Classification : F54, D62, L96

INTRODUCTION

The space economy is no longer just a technology-driven sector; it has evolved into a more complex, multi-sectoral system of strategic importance. It has become a crucial aspect of economic development, public policy, and international relations. Specifically, satellite technology, in the form of positioning systems, earth observation, etc., poses multilayered externalities by serving end users from a variety of sectors, including communications, agriculture, disaster management, and defence (Gürtuna, 2013: 11–14). Due to their potential to deliver global goods, in some studies, these infrastructures have been defined as 'global public goods' (London Economics, 2015).

The space and economy have grown not only through public investment, but also with increasing commercial participation. Private company actors (e.g., SpaceX, Blue Origin, and Planet Labs) have all entered the space scene in the 2000s, leading to a growing commercialization of the production and distribution of space data. This commercialization has, in its turn, produced new forms of inequality in terms of data ownership and access to infrastructure (OECD, 2020: 8–13). The increasing centralisation of power over infrastructures intended to be common goods in the hands of a few private companies has raised debates on concepts such as digital colonialism and data sovereignty in outer space (Tkatchova, 2011: 4–6).

By doing so, the paper aims to emphasize that the space economy is more than just about economic growth and technological innovation – it is also closely tied to questions of global justice, data access, and governance principles. With reference to space infrastructures as global public goods, the study also aims to understand how issues such as data ownership, spectrum licensing, and governance mechanisms impact the creation of public value.

SPACE INFRASTRUCTURES: DEFINITION AND ECONOMIC ROLE

Space infrastructures are composed of three key constituents: the space segment, the ground segment, and the data chain. It includes the satellites in orbit and ground control stations that communicate with them, as well as the information systems technology that processes the acquired data (Tkatchova, 2011: 137–138).

The orbital altitude determines the class of the space segment. The Low Earth Orbit (LEO), ranging from approximately 500 to 2,000 kilometers in altitude, is home to observation satellites and satellite constellations that provide global internet services. The Medium Earth Orbit (MEO) between 2000 km and geostationary orbit is primarily used by global navigation satellite systems (GNSS) such as GPS. The most commonly used communication satellites are settled in the so-called Geostationary Orbit (GEO). It is at a distance of approximately 35786 km from the Earth's center (Gürtuna, 2013). Each of these segments has important functional, data distribution, and serving roles to play that are essential for the continuation of worldwide communication and observation systems.

The ground segment comprises antennas, control centers, and the networks used to communicate with satellites. This module supports mission control, telemetry, tracking, and data operations. To operate multiple satellites that handle uninterrupted data flow, secure and low-latency systems are indispensable. All the elements between receiving raw data broadcast by satellites and end users, including processing, storage, and the final production of services, are part of this chain. Increasingly, these mechanisms, including large-scale data architectures, utilize AI-based analysis systems (Tkatchova, 2011: 137–138).

While these three layers reflect the technological side of space infrastructure, they are also strata in which great economic value is produced. Space structures are individually generating not only economic added value within the space sector, but also in almost all types of industrial production, including land transport and mail costs, as well as agriculture, disaster prevention, banking service economy protection, and national security. LE-Case-for-Space (2015) reported that in 2014, space applications contributed £ 11.3 billion to the UK economy, with a significant portion of this value derived from indirect effects, including spillovers and externalities.

In transportation, navigation systems (Galileo and GPS) have significantly improved the efficiency of routing, fuel management, and time. In the field of agriculture, precision farming technologies and crop monitoring systems have also enhanced productivity. Space technology's advantage for disaster management lies in early warning systems (EWS) and remote sensing techniques that are used as a source of information to decrease the number of accidents, better planning, value-added support at every stage based on GIS, and temporary support depending on EWS and remote sensing data (Gürtuna, 2013: 96–101). As outlined in the OECD (2019), effects of space infrastructure are also reflected by indirect GDP contributions, including public service efficiency, digital commerce, and active economic resilience. In the case of LEO internet constellations, in particular, there are indirect ways to enhance human capital productivity, specifically by ameliorating the digital divide.

As a result, the space economy has transitioned from an area of technological innovation to a multifaceted system with growing centrality in economic development, service delivery, and international relations. This evolution has been consolidating and advancing as new applications of satellite technologies for sectors such as communications, disaster management, agriculture, or defense (Gürtuna, 2013) have been successfully integrated. A comprehensive handbook has been published by the OECD (2022), offering a methodological framework for defining, measuring, and managing the space economy. It highlights that this entails creating high economic value not only in terms of direct outputs but also indirect externalities.

The positive externalities of space infrastructure services are described in the literature across several sectors. For example, the London Economics (2015) report suggests that the direct effect is approximately £6 billion per annum in UK GDP, which consists largely of value added in indirect sectors such as defence, transport, and financial services. This suggests that space infrastructures should be examined from the perspective of classical public goods theory, as a factor that not only affects the space industry but also numerous sectors of the economy and society.

However, the positive effects of space infrastructures are now overshadowed by the fact that data production and distribution are highly centralised in a few actors. The increasingly commercial function of space is causing asymmetries in data ownership and infrastructure access (Tkatchova, 2011). This opinion tangentially engages the literature on digital colonialism. Kwet (2019) explains digital colonialism in the context of the monopolization of global data infrastructure by predominantly U.S.-based private companies, emphasizing the concentration of control over software, hardware, and the data chain. The generation and command of spatial data byproducts have therefore become a geopolitical tool, rather than just an economic asset. According to the astropolitical approach, Dolman (2002) considers the capacity of space infrastructures to be composed of three elements: superiority, control over data, orbital access (from astronauts to astronauts), and launch inversion.

The economy of space has unique features compared to terrestrial economies, such as networked economies, scale economies, and knowledge intensity, with high fixed costs (OECD, 2020). Space infrastructures are more than physical systems; they are public goods with global economic externalities. These features challenge the reconsideration of public policies and international legislation.

EXTERNALITIES IN THE SPACE ECONOMY: PUBLIC GOODS AND ENVIRONMENTAL RISKS

Space infrastructures provide social benefits that extend beyond their economic returns, making significant contributions in crucial areas such as disaster response, education, and environmental monitoring, including efforts to combat climate change. In its essence, these advantages are known in the economic literature as positive externalities (Gümüş, 2000: 67). More precisely, third-party profits from investments made by individuals or the private sector that are not completely reflected in market prices are considered societal benefits (Papandreou, 1998: 58–59). The services provided by space infrastructures are frequently characterised as global public goods from an economic standpoint, given their worldwide applicability and the benefits they bring to people beyond arbitrary territorial or political divisions (London Economics, 2015).

The classification has also been challenged by the commercialization of satellite data production and distribution, as well as an emerging trend toward increased citations for patents on natural resources that reference geospatial data. By definition, pure public goods have two properties, non-excludability and non-rivalry "non-exclusive", meaning that no one can be excluded from using the good (by preventing others from using it) and one person's use of the good does not reduce its availability to others. The present organization of the space economy, however, works against these ideals. For example, many high-resolution observation data or high-bandwidth communication channels are managed under commercial licenses and subscription fees, making these services effectively excludable (Weinzierl, 2018). According to Gürtuna (2018: 24–25), private access based on the monetization of datasets hinders their otherwise open availability and thus the occurrence of positive externalities. This results in a concrete form of data colonialism affecting already critical public services, such as disaster response or agriculture, which are produced and maintained by communities in the Global South, but whose access to basic information has become subject to commercial market prices (Couldry & Mejias, 2019).

In the same manner, radio frequency spectrum and geostationary orbit slots are natural resources that are scarce and at risk of depletion (space debris), therefore becoming rivalrous (Tkatchova, 2011: 200). The consequence is that orbital resources no longer behave simply as pure public goods; instead, they have assumed characteristics of a common-pool resource (CPR) whose congestion and overuse are aggravated by commercial demands (OECD, 2022: 165). This shift re-concentrates control of space infrastructures in the hands of a small number of companies, continuing to deprive countries with limited national budgets of access and exacerbating structural asymmetries.

In disaster management, satellite imagery plays a crucial role in providing accurate and timely images before and after natural events, such as wildfires, floods, or earthquakes. In such situations, telecommunication satellites can play a crucial role in the emergency communication infrastructure (Gürtuna, 2013). Additionally, monitoring environmental parameters is used to optimize crop productivity and manage water resources effectively. In this connection, space technologies are said to have a dramatic impact on rural development policies, specifically in emerging economies (Tkatchova, 2011: 11–13). Positive spillovers are also observed in the field

of education, particularly in remote regions where satellite internet offers improved access to educational resources. In the context of SDGs, such information suggests that the potential social impacts of infrastructure in space cannot be neglected alongside an economic rationale. Another area of vital importance is mitigating the impact of climate change. Satellite observations are very important for quantifying environmental variables, such as greenhouse gas emissions, sea level rise, deforestation, and glacier melting. The expanding utilization of space technologies for environmental sustainability and climate modeling is exemplified in a NASA (2018) report.

However, while space infrastructures offer numerous advantages, they also generate hazards and negative externalities that can threaten the sustainability of the space economy. Negative externalities, whereby a producer or consumer imposes costs on third parties that are not reflected in the price they are willing to pay for another's product, can be associated with exhaustible resources (Jakhu & Pelton, 2017).

Figure 1. Space Junk
(Source: The European Space Agency (ESA), 2025)

Space debris is considered the most significant negative externality of space projects. Decades of launching satellites and placing them in orbit have left the space around Earth filled with hazardous fragments. Once you reach a critical mass, these pieces will run into each other and create even more fragments—the so-called cascading effect that can mean well-functioning satellites failing and whole orbit zones becoming off-limits for years to come. These places can only be made usable again through natural orbital decay or through complex engineering solutions (Gürtuna, 2018: 53).

Over the past 60 years of space exploration, more than 5,200 launches have placed approximately 7,500 satellites into or near the thermosphere, with over half of these (~4,300) remaining in space a decade ago. However, only around 1,200 satellites are still active. The aggregate weight of this debris amounts to over 7,500 tonnes, and it is threatening active space

ventures. As reported by the Secure World Foundation (2020), the levels of pollutants in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) are growing unchecked, increasing the threat of scenarios with irreversible orbital congestion known as Kessler Syndrome. However, as shown in Figure 2, space debris is accumulating: old satellites, debris from wrecked spacecraft, and remnants from collisions. Even objects too small to track can be very destructive, as demonstrated by the cherry-sized metal fragment traveling at orbital velocity (which contains the explosive power of a hand grenade!). Current estimates indicate 23,000 objects >10 cm, around 500,000 fragments between 1 and 10 cm, and >100 million particles smaller than 1 cm are in orbit within LEO (Weinzierl, 2018: 186).

Figure 2. Monthly count of objects in Earth orbit by object type
(Source: Weinzierl, 2018: 186)

While space debris is a textbook case of bad economic externalities, the lack of ownership and regulation in the outer-space environment restricts many standard Earth-based options. For instance, the Coasean solution to externalities via bargaining among affected parties becomes null and void in space for lack of clearly defined property rights (Coase, 1960). Although Pigouvian taxes and fiscal measures have been proposed, the lack of a central global government to enforce them is a significant hurdle (Hanson, 2016). Additionally, while Elinor Ostrom's (2010) model of polycentric governance may appear ideal in theory, it is not practical without proper monitoring and enforcement in outer space. Due to these specifications and the lack of a centralized global governance system, the issue is expected to lead to negative consequences similar to a "tragedy of the commons", as noted by Weinzierl (2018).

The challenge of interference also urgently remains to be addressed. The RF spectrum is the lifeblood of communication satellites' ability to send and receive information. The commoditization of the spectrum has led to large private companies licensing huge tracts of this

resource, literally preventing smaller nations and agencies from accessing it. It is a challenge regarding governance, which must find a way of efficient regulation along with stronger global cooperation (Gürtuna, 2018: 24-25).

Not only are there environmental hazards in space, but also those due to space environmental risks do not confine themselves exclusively to orbital altitudes. Spacecraft and rocket re-entry debris may also impact terrestrial habitats. Furthermore, the rocket propellants, which deploy hydrochloric acid, for example, also produce toxic gases in the atmosphere, polluting it. As reported by the OECD (2019), regulations related to the environmental effects of space infrastructures at the international level are currently inadequate. It appeals to the space-related environmental externalities to be viewed within a universal system of international space environmental law.

DIGITAL COLONIALISM AND THE CYCLE OF DEPENDENCE

While digital colonialism is being used to describe the centralisation of data production and command in some dominant agents globally (Nothias, 2025: 2). Such a structural hegemony leads to the concentration of dominion over the triad of components at the base level of digital ecology—software, hardware, and network access—in a few powerful hands. This is especially true in the new space economy, particularly as it relates to satellite data. The United States now owns the majority of satellites, along with European Union member states and China. Privately-owned companies based in these areas (e.g., Maxar Technologies, Planet Labs, Amazon (Kuiper), SpaceX (Starlink)) now dominate the global market for the production and distribution of observational, communication, and navigation data (Kwet, 2019: 2-7). The data monopolization that results in allows private companies to block access, covering the entire value chain – from data generation to actual analysis, thereby turning this into a crime of commodifying data ownership. The publicly generated data, which has become essential for public services, is now mostly available through commercial licenses, and the corporate policies of such firms restrict access to these licenses. The data-driven economic system is now exclusionary. Although Gürtuna (2013) does not explicitly use the term "digital colonialism", he highlights the access asymmetries caused by the privatization of the space sector.

Now, the few actors' concentration of space-based data production and control at the global level further continues to enhance the developing countries' status as consumers, pointing to the Dependency theory as proposed by Andre Gunder Frank. Frank is here seen as representing the system of the world made up of core and appendix countries, a dependence relationship between these systemic structures which now reflects within the space economy in the form of a new cycle of dependency (Kay, 2005: 1178 -1180). However, this pattern has acquired new meanings in the literature since the period of digital colonialism(man) (Kwet, 2019: 2-7). Contrary to Dependency Theory's attention to the movement of capital and labour between periphery and core, digital colonialism emphasizes ownership over knowledge, platforms, and data (Nothias, 2025: 2). These two structural problems are deeply connected in the space economy. The developing world is unable to acquire high-resolution satellite data (that is vital for agriculture, environmental monitoring, and disaster management) from data vendors (commercial license with a blanket coverage held mostly by U.S.-EU-founded companies). Payment to use such licenses can be interpreted as a capital outflow and is a knowledge-based follow-up on the dependency mechanisms, suggested by Frank (Tkatchova, 2011: 166). This imagined largesse, reflecting the transfer of wealth predicted by Dependency Theory, now finds its fruition embedded in only a 'belief', produced by digital colonialism in the form of data monopolies. The result is that

peripheral countries are not only obliged to be status data consumers but also pay increasingly low fees for access to space infrastructures, turning part of their national budgets towards the data monopolies of central economies. This could be with technical, but also threatens political sovereignty as it enforces a continuing loss of data sovereignty through economic dependence (Dolman, 2002: 21).

This cycle is especially observable in the Global South, where life's essential demands are defined through outside-controlled mechanisms. In Sub-Saharan Africa, for instance, high-resolution satellite imagery (vital to food security and agricultural productivity) is a monopoly business interest of US- and EU-based space companies like Planet Labs and Maxar Technologies (Nothias, 2025: 4). Such sovereign governments may have to pay up to enter into costly licensing agreements for obtaining this key data on crop health, water availability and the forecast of droughts within their country. This gives us two dependencies:

Economic dependency: Money in the form of data licenses with no end date continues to flow out as capital and resources from already thinly stretched budgets to big tech monopolies, thus affirming Dependency theory's thesis of financial flows towards comfort through the prism of our age – that is, Data.

Data and technology dependence: These nations are also dependent on software infrastructure and knowledge for data processing and interpretation. If foreign private enterprises own the data that are driving strategic decisions, this weakens national data sovereignty and independence in strategy (Tkatchova, 2011: 149-151).

Peripheral countries are therefore unable to "close the development gap" despite their own use of resources and labor to power growth in core countries, such that they remain structurally underdeveloped (Kay, 2005: 1178–1180). This framework is being replicated inside the space economy. Core countries dominate the production, distribution, and infrastructure of satellite data, while peripheral nations are relegated to being "data consumers." As shown in Fig. 3, an inheritance pattern and a locally based dependency cycle are associated with the asymmetrical construction. Although the number of (other) countries with satellites has increased, in other words, suggesting more widespread technical access to production processes and ownership investment is still monopolized by the same core centers.

Figure 3. Countries with Satellites (1966-2020)
(Source: Union of Concerned Scientists (UCS), 2024)

The countries that have possessed satellites between 1966 and 2020 are pictured in Figure 3. Traditionally, access to space technology has had a strong, centralized, and asymmetrical character. In the 1960s, only a few countries had satellite launch and data command capabilities, primarily the United States (US) and the Soviet Union (USSR) (United Nations, 1967). A review of geographical maps from that time demonstrates that almost all other countries were in an observer status, with a heavy dependence on external access to space technologies and information resources (UCS, 2024). Perhaps the most profound implication of this structure was the concentration of data production, resulting in massive imbalances in global knowledge flows. Satellite applications were numerous, from strategic military intelligence and geopolitical analysis

to climate monitoring and even agricultural surveillance. However, the data was little shared and mostly unavailable, which would strengthen not only technical but also political and economic monopolies (Gürtuna, 2013: 49–50). By 2020, a more apparently inclusive portrait had developed. More than a hundred nations already possessed satellites, and many had begun to develop their own national space programs. Some regions, in fact, Southeast Asia, Africa, and Latin America started to use them for remote sensing, agricultural monitoring, and disaster early warning systems through satellites (Tkatchova, 2011: 166). Although this numerical proliferation has occurred, the asymmetrical nature of the critical space infrastructure framework remains intact. Few countries, all told some eight (the United States, China, Russia, India, Japan and France to say nothing of Iran Israel and North Korea) still control launch systems at all. Additionally, high-value-added sectors, such as satellite production and the allocation of orbital slots, are still predominantly dominated by state-affiliated private firms in industrialized countries. Thus, a form of digital colonialism has taken hold in space: developing countries can own a satellite today, but are unable to launch it; they can utilize the infrastructure without being able to govern it; they may obtain data, but lack guidance on how it is generated. This organization reveals that the de facto monopolies of the 1960s are being replicated in new technological guises in the 21st century. As such, the race for space technology and satellite development should not be seen as a win-win situation heralding 'the withering away of global inequalities'. To the contrary, these trends suggest that inequality is simply taking on a different form. There are still profound inequalities in data generation, stewardship, and ownership. Since the launch of the first satellite, Sputnik, in 1957, the number of countries with space activities has grown significantly. There has been a recent surge in satellite launch capabilities among new entrants especially over the past decade. Approximately 30 new space agencies have been established worldwide, in both developed and developing countries (OECD, 2022: 21).

Figure 4 The logarithm of the success frequency that each country became a satellite owner who registered in orbit and/or launched rockets, based on (a) the number of countries registering satellites into orbits (b) the number of launching rockets. The chart below shows the total number of countries that have successfully launched their first satellite or gained independent access to space through domestic launches from 1957 to 2020. Years are presented in the horizontal axis, and the number of countries in the vertical axis are shown. Bars indicate countries that became satellite owners for the first time, and diamond symbols represent countries that acquired independent rocket launch capacity.

The most obvious observation that jumps off the page from Figure 4 is that, although the number of satellite-owning countries has been increasing, the number of independent launch-capable states remains extremely sparse. In particular, after the 2000s, we have seen a clear rise in the number of satellite-owning countries, whereas the number of states able to launch satellites on their own into space has followed a straight-line trajectory.

Figure 4. Number of countries that have registered satellites in orbit and/or successfully launched rockets
(Source: OECD, 2022)

In the medium term, large space agencies like NASA, the CSA, or the CNES have also begun to use economists or invest in organization-wide data gathering operations. Likewise, organizations such as the European Space Agency (ESA) have created dedicated teams to map the space economy and have worked with the OECD to disseminate best practices worldwide. MOREOVER, at a time when the space activities of governments have become more closely linked to economic and social policy goals, the need for better data and indicators has become ever greater (OECD, 2022: 21–22).

For this purpose, various countries and organizations currently conduct surveys, as well as economic impact and sectoral studies, on the space industry. Cases include the US Satellite Account, national studies in Germany, Australia, France, Italy, and the UAE, as well as Denmark's attempt to calculate its space economy. However, there is a general lack of comparability in the data across countries and over time that complicates the assessment of public spending effectiveness. Thus, the OECD (2022) has launched a multistakeholder consultation to harmonize definitions and metrics for the space economy, concluding that there is a need for a worldwide recognized common framework.

The ability to launch rockets independently is a sign not just of a country's technology but its strategic independence. When a country cannot do this, it is not just technologically dependent, but also politically and economically so. Even though more satellites are being launched, which might seem to be a signal of progress, they disguise a continued reliance on high-value segments for production, launch services, spectrum allocation, and data processing – all still dominated by countries and their corporations. Although Figure 4 suggests a quantitative democratization of space access, it simultaneously demonstrates the qualitative deepening of structural dependence.

This process reflects the contradiction between false development and the underlying structural dependency, as expressed by Dependency Theory (Frank, 1974). Emerging countries are the consumers of technology, but they are not yet technologists or decision-makers. It means the data sovereignty and strategic decision-making power in space are still largely concentrated in a small number of world powers.

CONCLUSION

The space economy is no longer a purely technical field but rather a multidimensional global activity where strategic and economic interests meet. However, from the lens of Andre Gunder Frank's Dependency Theory, this extension appears to replicate structural dependencies in the form of data monopolies and infrastructure ownership by core countries. The commercialisation of satellite data highlights a new cycle of capital valorization that was strengthened through digital colonialism.

Although satellite ownership has clearly increased, this expansion is a numbers illusion that hides the structural differences due to an absence of independent launch and data processing capacity. Decoupling from the cycle of structural asymmetry and digital colonialism requires an urgent fundamental overhaul of international space governance and financial mechanisms. First, the International Telecommunication Union (ITU) needs to move from the outdated 'use it or lose it' approach to a new regime based on 'fair use and benefit sharing'. In practice, this might mean implementing some form of set-aside quota or shared frequency bands for emerging countries – specifically about scarce goods like radio frequency spectrum and orbital slots (especially in LEO) (Tkatchova, 2011).

A global and normative framework to delegitimize the data monopolies that form the bedrock of digital colonialism must be constructed under COPUOS. A first step in this would be to establish International Emergency Data Protocols that apply to all commercial satellite operators. These protocols would ensure the free or cost-based access to commercial HR data used in emergencies during natural disasters and humanitarian crises in developing countries. Moreover, it would be a public-interest precedent to current regimes of data ownership – a way to ensure that these positive externalities of space are forever enshrined in international law.

Redress financial dependence and technological servitude, to the degree that they are interrelated problems: It is necessary to treat data as a public utility. This could involve establishing a Global Public Licensing Fund, funded by the wealthiest nations and private companies that generate substantial profits from space data services. The fund would issue free or discounted public licenses to key Earth observation data (for agriculture, water, disaster risk management, and other areas) to countries in the Global South.

However, as we know, access to data is not enough — what good is the ability to access new data if there are no tools available to help interpret that information? On top of being an investor in open-source data processing platforms and AI-based analytics tools, it would be beneficial for a fund like this one to also invest in their development and distribution. This would enable countries to make strategic, data-driven decisions based on national priorities, free from foreign technology monopolies, thereby liberating them from the technological tyranny of digital colonialism.

The democratization of the space economy is not possible without the equitable involvement of developing countries in production, data processing, and global governance mechanisms. It is not optional to guarantee global data justice and digital sovereignty—because only then can we dismantle the root structural inequities of the space economy.

Author Contributions: The entire study has been prepared by a single author.

Peer-review: Externally peer-reviewed

Conflict of Interest: The author has no conflicts of interest to declare.

Ethical Committee Approval: Ethics committee approval is not required.

Yazar Katkıları: Makalenin bütünü tek bir yazar tarafından hazırlanmıştır.

Hakem Değerlendirmesi: Dış bağımsız.

Çıkar Çatışması: Yazar, çıkar çatışması olmadığını beyan etmiştir.

Etik Kurul Belgesi: Etik kurul onay belgesi gerektirmemektedir.

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